

Prediction of Reservoir Parameters using Support Vector Machines, A Machine Learning Approach

*Pothana Prasad**, *Soma Chatterjee*, *VLN Avadhani* and *PP Deo*
CEWELL, Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Ltd, Vadodara, India
***Prasad_Pothana@ongc.co.in**

Support Vector Machine Regression, Machine Learning, Petrophysics, Well Logging

Summary

Reservoir parameters such as effective porosity, clay volume, and water saturation are essential in estimating the hydrocarbon reserves in place. Well logs are continuous measurements of the physical properties of the formation. Quantitative interpretation of well logs coupled with core calibration can give reservoir parameter estimates, which can be good approximates to that of core results. Thus, well log analysis is a practical alternative to the expensive and time-consuming core studies. Various core-based non-linear mathematical models are used for this purpose.

Support vector machines regression (SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm, which can be used for regression and classification problems. A support-vector machine uses kernel trick to constructs a set of hyperplanes in a high- or infinite-dimensional feature spaces of the inputs to solve the non-linear regression problems. In the present study, the application of SVMs in estimating the clay volume and effective porosity from well logs are examined. First, the algorithm is applied to synthetic data to test the applicability and parameter optimization. Further SVM is trained and tested on siliciclastic formations and found acceptable results. The root mean squared error between SVM predicted and manually interpreted results is for VCL is 0.007 and PHIE is 0.005.

Introduction

Petrophysics plays a key role in hydrocarbon reservoir identification and its production potential. Reservoir parameters such as clay volume (VCL), effective porosity (PHIE) and Water saturation (SW) among others are essential in estimating the hydrocarbons in-place. Core analysis gives the realistic estimates of these reservoirs; however, they are expensive and consume considerable time. On the other hand, well logs are the continuous physical measurements of the formation. The well logs are quantitatively interpreted and calibrated with cores for the estimation of reservoir parameters. Several empirical and theoretical non-linear models are used for this purpose (Leveaux and Poupon 1971; Clavier, Coates, and Dumanoir 1984; Waxman and Smits 1968). However, selecting the appropriate model and estimating realistic reservoir parameters is difficult because of reservoir complexity. The complexity increases when dealing with carbonate, unconventional and tight reservoirs (Bust, Oletu, and Worthington 2011). A machine learning model doesn't need to be a functional form of dependency among well logs and the reservoir parameters. It can learn from the data itself, which can handle non-linear complexity effectively when properly trained.

In recent years, an emerging trend of applications of artificial intelligence, machine learning and big data analytics in petroleum industry can be seen (Xu 2019). Various machine learning algorithms such as artificial neural networks, random forest, self-organizing maps, support vector machines, etc, are used for lithology classification, pseudo-log generation, reservoir characterization etc (Heydari, Amirpour, and Ahmadi 2016; Akkurt et al., n.d.; Meshalkin et al. 2018; Alrumah and Ertekin 2019; Wai Wong et al. 2005).

SVM for prediction of Reservoir parameters

In the present study application of support vector machine regression is examined to predict the reservoir parameters such as clay volume (VCL) and effective porosity (PHIE). In this paper, first, the brief theory of SVM is given, then SVM is applied to synthetic data to test the performance and parameter optimization, and finally, SVM is applied to real data of siliciclastic formations.

Theory

Support vector machines is a supervised machine learning algorithm, which can be used for both regression and classification problems. Given training vectors $x_i \in \mathfrak{R}^p$, $i=1 \dots n$, and a vector $y \in \mathfrak{R}^n$, ε -SVR solves the following primal problem (Cortes, Vapnik, and Saitta 1995; Smola and Scholkopf 2004)

$$\min \frac{1}{2} w^T w + C \sum_{i=1}^n (\zeta_i + \zeta_i^*)$$

Subject to

$$y_i - w^T \phi(x_i) - b \leq \varepsilon + \zeta_i$$

$$-y_i + w^T \phi(x_i) + b \leq \varepsilon + \zeta_i^*$$

$$\zeta_i, \zeta_i^* \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, n$$

Its dual is

$$\min_{\alpha, \alpha^*} \frac{1}{2} (\alpha - \alpha^*)^T Q (\alpha - \alpha^*) + \varepsilon e^T (\alpha + \alpha^*) - y^T (\alpha - \alpha^*)$$

Subject to

$$e^T (\alpha - \alpha^*) = 0$$

$$0 \leq \alpha, \alpha^* \leq C, i = 1, \dots, n$$

The decision function is

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha - \alpha_i^*) K(x_i, x) + \rho$$

Where, $Q \equiv K(x_i, x_j) = \phi(x_i)^T \phi(x_j)$ is the kernel, e is the unit vector and C is the upper bound, which is a trade of parameter between correct classification and margin between decision functions. Function ϕ implicitly maps the training vectors into a higher dimensional space. The detailed description of the SVR mathematical formulation is given in (Smola and Scholkopf 2004). The program implementation is carried out in Python and used scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al. 2011; Buitinck et al. 2013; van Rossum and Drake 2011). In the present study x_i corresponds to the input logs and the y corresponds to the VCL and PHIE.

Application of SVM on synthetic data

The synthetic model consists of 12 different units as shown in table-1. The model consists of mainly three lithofacies; clean sandstone, shaly sand, and shale. Each lithounit consists of different volume fractions of Sandstone, Shale, Water, and Hydrocarbon. First four units consist of clean sandstone. In the units from VI to XII, increasing amounts of clay volume is introduced gradually.

In this study, the applicability of the SVM in the context of petrophysical evaluation is more emphasized than the actual data complexity itself. Hence, while examining SVM on synthetic data, the following

SVM for prediction of Reservoir parameters

assumptions are made for simplicity 1) The properties of shales and sandstone are uniform and constant among all the units 2) The porosity exhibited by shale is not considered in the calculation of effective porosity. 3) Assumed no invasion. It is also assumed that the sandstone has a fixed porosity of 25%.

The conventional logs GR, RHOB, NPHI, and DT are estimated using a linear combination of log responses of individual constituent's fractional volume at each depth (Quirein et al. 1986; Malkoti, Vedanti, and Bhattacharya, n.d.), which can be formulated as

Model	Unit	VCL (V/V)	SW	Remarks
	I	0.00	0.25	Clean Sandstone with varying water saturations
	II	0.00	0.50	
	III	0.00	0.75	
	IV	0.00	1.00	
	V	0.95	1.00	Shale
	VI	0.10	0.25	Shaly Sand with varying Saturations
	VII	0.20	0.5	
	VIII	0.30	0.5	
	IX	0.30	0.75	
	X	0.50	1.0	
	XI	0.75	1.0	
	XII	1.00	1.0	Shale

Table 1: Synthetic model and corresponding model parameters

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i V_i + \varepsilon$$

Where, L = Cumulative log response of all the constituents, n is the total the number of constituents, V_i is the volume fraction of the i^{th} constituent, w_i is the log response of i^{th} constituent. ε = noise. In the present study normal random noise is added to the data. Log responses of different constituents are given in table-2.

Const.	GR (gAPI)	NPHI (V/V)	RHOB (g/cc)	DT (us/ft)	RT (ohmm)
CLAY	200	0.53	2.75	110	3.0
SAND	0.5	-0.03	2.64	56	999.0
WATER	0.5	1.0	1.0	190	10.0
OIL	0.5	0.8	0.5	230	100.0
A = 1.0, m = 2.0, n = 2.0, RW = 0.5 ohmm,					

Table-2: Parameters used in synthetic data generation

SVM for prediction of Reservoir parameters

Indonesian equation is used to estimate synthetic deep resistivity data (Leveaux and Poupon 1971). The parameters used in the computation is given in table-2.

$$\frac{1}{R_t} = S_w^n \left[\left(\frac{V_{sh}^{2-V_{sh}}}{R_{sh}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{\phi_e^m}{R_w} \right)^{1/2} \right]^2$$

Where R_t = Deep resistivity, S_w = water saturation, V_{sh} = shale volume, R_{sh} = Resistivity of the shale, ϕ_e = effective porosity, R_w = Formation water resistivity, n = Saturation exponent, m = Constant related to cementation factor and tortuosity.

SVR is not scale-invariant, hence before training the model the data should be standardized. In the present study, the data is standardized to have mean 0 and variance 1. The same scaling is applied while predicting the results. Radial basis function kernel is used in the SVM algorithm and $C=1$. The synthetic data along with the testing results are plotted in figure-1.

Application of SVM on real data sets

Two wells well-1 and well-2, located in Krishna Godavari Basin, India were studied to predict the clay volume and effective porosity. The formation studied is siliciclastic, which is deposited during the Oligocene to Miocene Age. Manual interpretation of petrophysical evaluation is already carried out by petrophysical experts. In the well-1, a total 2240 depth points are used for training and testing. Data is split randomly 70% and 30%, and used for training and testing. All the data is standardized to have mean 0 and variance 1. The same optimal parameters of SVM obtained from the synthetic data analysis is used for the real data. At each depth input logs viz, GR, RT, RHOB and NPHI are used for the input training sets. In the first step, VCL is predicted from the set of input logs. In the second step, VCL is taken as input along with the input logs to predict PHIE.

The training and testing in the well is shown in Figure-2. In well-2 using the input logs viz, GR, RT, RHOB, and NPHI, predicted first VCL and then PHIE. The predicted results along with the manual interpreted results are presented in Figure-3 The root mean squared (RMS) error between SVM predicted and manually interpreted results is for VCL is 0.007 and PHIE is 0.005.

SVM for prediction of Reservoir parameters

Figure 1 : Example of Synthetic data. Test data of VCLAY and PHIE are shown as green dots in track 3 and 4.

Figure 2 : Training and testing of SVM on well-1 data. Green dots overlaying the curves indicate the testing samples

SVM for prediction of Reservoir parameters

Figure 3: Application of SVM on well-2. Predicted VCLAY and PHIE curves are shown in green colour and the original data was shown in red colour in track 3 and track 4

Conclusions

In this study, the application of SVM for the prediction of reservoir parameters VCL and PHIE is examined. An SVM uses kernel trick to constructs a set of hyperplanes in a high- or infinite-dimensional feature spaces of the inputs to solve the non-linear regression problems. Although the choice of the kernel is subjective, SVM using the radial basis function kernel is effective in the present study. The RMS error between the predicted and manually interpreted results is very small. It is noted that in this study a simple problem of the conventional reservoir is demonstrated, however, SVM has more potential to address wide variety of complex issues, which needs to be investigated. The applications of SVM in solving the issues related to unconventional reservoirs, carbonates, permeability characterization, etc are the future objective of the present study.

References

- Akkurt, Ridvan, Tim T Conroy, David Psaila, Andrea Paxton, Jacob Low, and Paul Spaans. n.d. "Accelerating and enhancing petrophysical analysis with machine learning: a case study of an automated system for well log outlier detection and reconstruction."
- Alrumah, Muhammad, and Turgay Ertekin. 2019. "Prediction of the Water Saturation around Wells with Bottom Water Drive Using Artificial Neural Networks," no. March. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JPGE2018.029>.
- Buitinck, Lars, Gilles Louppe, Mathieu Blondel, Fabian Pedregosa, Andreas Mueller, Olivier Grisel, Vlad Niculae, et al. 2013. "API Design for Machine Learning Software: Experiences from the Scikit-

SVM for prediction of Reservoir parameters

- Learn.” In *ECML PKDD Workshop: Languages for Data Mining and Machine Learning*, 108–22.
- Bust, Vivian K, Joshua U Oletu, and Paul F Worthington. 2011. “The Challenges for Carbonate Petrophysics in Petroleum Resource Estimation.” *SPE Reservoir Evaluation & Engineering* 14 (01): 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.2118/142819-PA>.
- Clavier, C, G Coates, and J Dumanoir. 1984. “Theoretical and Experimental Bases for the Dual-Water Model for Interpretation of Shaly Sands.” *Society of Petroleum Engineers Journal* 24 (02): 153–68. <https://doi.org/10.2118/6859-PA>.
- Cortes, Corinna, Vladimir Vapnik, and Lorenza Saitta. 1995. “Support-Vector Networks Editor.” *Machine Learning*. Vol. 20. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Heydari, Hamid, Masoud Amirpour, and Saeid Ahmadi. 2016. “Estimation of Water Saturation by Using Radial Based Function Artificial Neural Network in Carbonate Reservoir : A Case Study in Sarvak Formation Estimation of Water Saturation by Using Radial Based Function Arti Fi Cial Neural Network in Carbonate Reservoir : A Case Study in Sarvak Formation.” *Petroleum* 2 (2): 166–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petlm.2016.04.002>.
- Leveaux, Jacques, and Andre Poupon. 1971. “Evaluation Of Water Saturation In Shaly Formations.” *The Log Analyst* 12 (04): 6. <https://doi.org/>.
- Malkoti, Ajay, Nimisha Vedanti, and A K Bhattacharya. n.d. “Inversion of Well Log Data Using Improved Shale Model for Determination of Petrophysical Parameters.”
- Meshalkin, Yury, Dmitry Koroteev, Evgeniy Popov, Evgeny Chekhonin, and Yury Popov. 2018. “Robotized Petrophysics : Machine Learning and Thermal Profiling for Automated Mapping of Lithotypes in Unconventionals Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering Robotized Petrophysics : Machine Learning and Thermal pro Fi Ling for Automated Mapping of Lithotypes in Unconventionals.” *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, no. April: 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2018.03.110>.
- Pedregosa, F, G Varoquaux, A Gramfort, B Michel V.and Thirion, O Grisel, M Blondel, R Prettenhofer P.and Weiss, et al. 2011. “Scikit-Learn: Machine Learning in Python.” *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 12: 2825–30.
- Quirein, J, S Kimminau, J La Vigne, Julian Singer, and F Wendel. 1986. “A Coherent Framework For Developing And Applying Multiple Formation Evaluation Models.” *SPWLA 27th Annual Logging Symposium*. Houston, Texas: Society of Petrophysicists and Well-Log Analysts. <https://doi.org/>.
- Rossum, Guido van, and Fred L Drake. 2011. *The Python Language Reference Manual*. Network Theory Ltd.
- Smola, Alex J, and Bernhard Scholkopf. 2004. “A Tutorial on Support Vector Regression *.” *Statistics and Computing*. Vol. 14. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Wai Wong, Kok, Yew Soon Ong, Tamás D Gedeon, and Chun Che Fung. 2005. “Reservoir Characterization Using Support Vector Machines.”
- Waxman, M H, and L J M Smits. 1968. “Electrical Conductivities in Oil-Bearing Shaly Sands.” *Society of Petroleum Engineers Journal* 8 (02): 107–22. <https://doi.org/10.2118/1863-A>.
- Xu, Chicheng. 2019. “SPE-195068-MS When Petrophysics Meets Big Data: What Can Machine Do?”

Acknowledgement

Views expressed in this paper are those of author only. The authors acknowledge ONGC Management for giving the permission to publish the present work.